

Full Length Article

Development of a live cell assay for the zinc transporter ZnT8

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ABSTRACT

Zinc is an essential trace element that is involved in many biological processes and in cellular homeostasis. In pancreatic β -cells, zinc is crucial for the synthesis, processing, and secretion of insulin, which plays a key role in glucose homeostasis and which deficiency is the cause of diabetes. The accumulation of zinc in pancreatic cells is regulated by the solute carrier transporter SLC30A8 (or Zinc Transporter 8, ZnT8), which transports zinc from cytoplasm in intracellular vesicles. Allelic variants of SLC30A8 gene have been linked to diabetes. Given the physiological intracellular localization of SLC30A8 in pancreatic β -cells and the ubiquitous endogenous expression of other Zinc transporters in different cell lines that could be used as cellular model for SLC30A8 recombinant over-expression, it is challenging to develop a functional assay to measure SLC30A8 activity. To achieve this goal, we have firstly generated a HEK293 cell line stably overexpressing SLC30A8, where the over-expression favors the partial localization of SLC30A8 on the plasma membrane. Then, we used the combination of this cell model, commercial FluoZin-3 cell permeant zinc dye and live cell imaging approach to follow zinc flux across SLC30A8 over-expressed on plasma membrane, thus developing a novel functional imaging-based assay specific for SLC30A8. Our novel approach can be further explored and optimized, paving the way for future small molecule medium-throughput screening.

1. Introduction

Zinc is a trace element known to be an essential nutrient for life in mammals, and it plays a key role in growth, development, immunity, and many other biological processes [1–5]. Zinc homeostasis results from a coordinated regulation of metallothioneins and membrane transporters belonging to the ZIP and ZnT families, which are responsible of the uptake, excretion and intracellular storage / trafficking of this important element [6–8]. ZnTs belong to the solute carrier 30 family (SLC30) of transporters and regulate the passage of zinc across biological membranes out of the cytosol, while ZIPs belong to the SLC39 family and they transport zinc into the cytosol [7,8].

Disruption of zinc homeostasis due to transporter malfunction is observed in several pathologies affecting humans, such as cancer, inflammation, diabetes mellitus and in neurological diseases [4,9–15].

Diabetes is an illness characterized by loss of number and function of

pancreatic β cells, which leads to development of diabetes type 1 (T1DM) or type 2 (T2DM). Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have associated SLC30A8 (ZnT8) with an increase in the risk of the development of T2DM [12,16]. SLC30A8 functions as a Zinc / H^+ exchanger expressed exclusively in pancreas and mainly in pancreatic β cells [17–19]. It is localized to insulin secretory granules where it facilitates the accumulation of zinc from the cytoplasm into intracellular vesicles and is implicated in secretion of insulin from beta cells facilitating insulin hexamer formation [20,21]. The non-synonymous variant encoding a tryptophan-to-arginine switch at position 325 (Arg325Trp, caused by SLC30A8 rs13266634 polymorphism) resulted to be associated with T2DM [9,12,16,22]. 46 % of European non-diabetic offspring of T2DM patients are rs13266634 homozygotes; they are diabetes-prone and characterized by a 19 % decrease in first-phase insulin release following an intravenous glucose load [22]. This SNP was confirmed to be associated with T2DM in a study of 500+ Japanese patients [23] and

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in Chinese population [24]. Another non-synonymous SNP, also affecting codon 325 (Arg325Gln, rs16889462) was associated with increased repaglinide (an insulin secretagogue agent, safe and effective medication for T2DM) efficacy in Chinese type 2 diabetes mellitus patients [25]. The rs16889462 polymorphism in SLC30A8 was found to be common in Africans (MAF = 10.5 %) and East Asians (MAF = 8 %), but rare in all other populations analyzed (MAF < 1 %) [26].

However, the role of SLC30A8 in diabetes risk remains still controversial [9,27,28]. For long time, p.R325, the most frequent variant of SLC30A8, has long been considered to possess zinc transportation activity inferior to that of the p. W325 variant (in which arginine is replaced by tryptophan at position 325 of ZnT8) and is associated with a higher risk of diabetes than the p. W325 variant [9,29]. This conclusion was based on ectopic overexpression (e.g., plasmid transfection or adenovirus infection) in either a mouse or rat tumor cell line [30,31] (fluorescence- and radioactivity-based studies on the rodent pancreatic β -cell lines MIN6 and INS-1E overexpressing W or R variants of ZnT8). Recently, another study with purified SLC30A8 incorporated into an artificial proteoliposome bilayer or recombinantly expressed in human embryonic kidney (HEK293) cells has shown that p.R325 variant is hyperactive and exhibits accelerated zinc transport compared to p. W325 variant, associated with a lower risk [32], which contradicts previous conclusions from rodent tumor cell lines, but is consistent with human genetic results that the rare loss of function ZnT8 mutations decreases the risk of diabetes. Other studies showed that in HEK293 cells and in *Xenopus laevis* oocytes no detectable differences were found in zinc transport between W and R variants (zinc transport assay using the Zinc radioactive isotope) [33]. Altogether, more evidence is needed to make a solid conclusion on the comparison of zinc transport between the p. R325 and p. W325 variants [34]. The Q325 variant was not still characterized for the impact on Zinc transportation. Nevertheless, the rs13266634 and rs16889462 SNPs are both located in the C-terminal region of ZnT-8 protein, therefore both Q325 and W325 variants might reasonably result in transporter function change [25].

Despite this controversy, SLC30A8 constitutes an attractive target for drug discovery [27,35]. It was suggested that, based on the protective effect of haploinsufficiency, small molecules or RNA interference blocking SLC30A8 activity could be beneficial to prevent against T2DM [9]. However, given that the effect of SLC30A8 on diabetic risk is still not clear [27,28], other type modulators, such as transporter activators or chemical chaperons, may be needed in the future [36]. Therefore, robust functional assay screening platforms for SLC30A8 are needed to identify small molecules able to modulate the activity of this important target in diabetes.

In this article, we first determined that recombinant human SLC30A8 locates at the plasma membrane upon doxycycline-inducible overexpression in the Jump In T-REx Human Embryonic Kidney 293 cells lines (HEK293-JI). Next, we employed these cell model to measure zinc influx into the cytoplasm using a live cell-based imaging assay. In particular in this work the SLC30A8 was activated in 'reverse mode', i.e. providing a high dose of Zinc substrate from the external side of cells, thus creating a zinc gradient (a driving force for zinc) that pushes the transporter to function in reverse, thus bringing zinc from the cell exterior into the cytosol. The detection of zinc influx as a fluorescence increase was permitted by FluoZin-3, a highly sensitive and specific zinc sensor. To confirm the specificity of the SLC30A8 signal detection, we used a previously reported SLC30A8 variant with abolished / reduced Zinc-binding capability [19,37]. Finally, we applied our assay to test the function of the two most frequent SLC30A8 variants associated to diabetes mellitus by GWAS studies [9,38–40].

In summary, we have developed a novel cell-based imaging assay in miniaturized 384-well plate format. This assay, upon further optimization, could be potentially used for future drug discovery campaigns to find modulators of SLC30A8, an emerging therapeutic target for diabetes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell lines generation and biological reagents

The Jump In T-REx human embryonic kidney 293 cell line (HEK293 JI) expressing doxycycline-inducible human wild-type SLCs were generated by the RESOLUTE consortium () as described previously [41]. Briefly, codon-optimized sequences of the SLC genes (SLC30A8 and SLC12A6) were cloned into a modified pJTI™ R4 Dest CMV-TO pA vector (Thermo Fisher Scientific) containing TwinStrepTag (IBA life-sciences) and HA epitopes (SH tag) at the C or N terminus of the protein target. SLC30A8 mutants were generated using the Q5 Site-Directed Mutagenesis Kit (NEB) following the manufacturer's protocol. The following primer pairs (FW/RV) were used to introduce mutations to the WT sequence: CCGTCTGATCAACCTGACAAGC / TGTGCTGCATCGGT-CACC and CCGACTGGGCAACCTGTTTCAGTCTATC / TGCAC-GAAGGCTGCGCGC (SLC30A8^{D110N,D224N}); AGCAGCATCCtGGGACTC TCAGGTGG / GTTGCCACGTGGGCGGAC (SLC30A8^{R325W}); AGCAG-CATCCCAGGACTCTCAGGTGGTGGC / GTTGCCACGTGGGCGGAC (SLC 30A8^{R325Q}). All constructs were confirmed by Sanger sequencing. Finally, HEK293 JI stably expressing the SLC30A8 mutants were generated as mentioned above.

2.2. Cell culture

After thawing, HEK293 JI stably expressing all constructs were cultured in DMEM medium (Euroclone, ECB7501L) supplemented with 10 % FBS (Performance Plus, Gibco, 16,000,044) + 1 % UltraGlutamine (Biowhittaker, BE17–605E/U1) and 1 % Pen/Strep (Euroclone, ECB3001D), 5 μ g/mL Blasticidin (Invivogen, ant-bl-1) and 2 mg/mL Geneticin (Sigma, G8168) for one-two weeks.

2.3. Imaged-based functional assay using fluoZin-3

One day before seeding, black 384 well plates (Greiner, 781,091) were manually coated with Poly-d-Lysine (Gibco, A38904–01) diluted at final concentration of 50 μ g/mL (1 h at 37 °C). The day after, the different cell lines were detached from culture flasks and seeded at 10,000 cells/well in medium without Phenol Red (DMEM, Gibco, 11,880–028) supplemented with 10 % FBS (Performance Plus, Gibco, 16,000,044), 1 % UltraGlutamine (Biowhittaker, BE17–605/U1) and 5 % Pen/Strep (Euroclone, ECB3001D) on the precoated black 384 well plates and cells were induced with doxycycline at final concentration of 10 ng/mL (uninduced cells kept as negative control). The day of the assay, the cells were loaded with FluoZin-3, AM dye (Invitrogen, F24195, 2.5 μ M final concentration) dissolved in calcium-, magnesium-, and phosphate-free HBSS Buffer (5.4 mM Potassium Chloride, 137 mM Sodium Chloride, 16.8 mM d-glucose, 20 mM Hepes, pH 7.4) containing Pluronic F-127 (ThermoFisher, P3000MP, 0.02 % final concentration), Hoechst 33,342 (ThermoFisher, 62,249, 4 μ M final concentration) and EDTA (Lifetech, 15,575–038, 5 mM final concentration) for 45 mins at 37 °C. The cells were then washed three times with calcium-, magnesium-, and phosphate-free HBSS Buffer (automatically at Biotek Washer) to remove the excess of dye not internalized by cells. After washing, the cells were incubated with calcium-, magnesium-, and phosphate-free HBSS Buffer for a further 45 mins to allow complete de-esterification of intracellular AM esters at Room Temperature. Before imaging, HBSS was rinsed and replaced with a dose response of Zinc Chloride (Sigma Aldrich, 229,997) prepared up to 5 mM in Imaging solution (ThermoFisher, A14291DJ). The cells were co-stained with Hoechst for nuclei and immediately imaged using High Content Microscope Opera Phenix (Revvity) by means of 40x magnification. Image analysis was carried out in Harmony software (Revvity). Briefly, raw images were corrected for background, nuclei detected in the blue channel (Hoechst) and a ring region around the nuclei was generated to capture the cytosolic intensity signal of the FluoZin-3. An intensity threshold was set to

select population enriched in Zinc concentration. Results were exported as mean per well. Images from 3 different fields / well from 4 independent wells were obtained for each condition.

2.4. Immunofluorescence and imaging for target localization

9.000 cells were seeded in 96-well plates (Corning) coated with Poly-L-lysine (Sigma, P2658). 16 h after protein induction with 10 ng/ml doxycycline, cells were fixed and permeabilized in 100 % Methanol for 10 min at -20°C . Then cells were rehydrated with PBS (Sigma, D8537) and subsequently incubated in Blocking Buffer containing PBS and 5 % BSA (Sigma, A3912) for 1 h at room temperature. Next, samples were incubated simultaneously with anti-HA from rat (Roche, 60,789,700 1:1000) and anti-SLC1A5 from rabbit (Abcam, ab237704 1:100) antibodies overnight at 4°C . After two washing steps, cells were incubated with secondary antibodies anti-rat coupled to AlexaFluor 488 (ThermoFisher, A-11,006, 1:1000) and anti-rabbit coupled to AlexaFluor 568 (ThermoFisher, A-11,011, 1:1000) for 1 h at room temperature. For counter staining, DAPI (Sigma, D9542 10 mM) was diluted in PBS 1:1000 and added to the cells. Imaging of the plates was performed in the high-throughput microscope Opera-Phenix (Perkin Elmer) using a 40x objective. Images from 15 different fields / well from 2 independent wells were obtained for each condition.

2.5. Data and statistical analysis

The cells were imaged using Operetta and Opera Phenix. The images were analyzed with Harmony Software. The difference between the groups were analyzed using One-way Anova. For statistical analysis of the imaging data, a Šidák's multiple comparisons test was used to test each sample versus HEK-JI-SLC30A8 cells.

Raw immunofluorescence images were analyzed with Fiji [42]. Co-localization (Pearson's score) was determined for each image using a FIJI macro using the BIOP JACoP plugin [43]. For statistical analysis of the imaging data, a Dunett's test was used to test each sample versus the HEK-JI-SLC30A8 sample and it was corrected for multiple testing with the Benjamini-Hochberg correction. Data was plotted using Prism 9 (GraphPad).

3. Results

3.1. Expression and subcellular localization of SLC30A8 overexpressed in HEK293-JI cells

We first generated HEK293-JI cells overexpressing SLC30A8 fused to a TwinStrepTag-HA (SH) epitope (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8) at the C (SLC30A8-SH) or N (SH-SLC30A8) terminus upon doxycycline induction. We then characterized the expression of the SLC30A8 protein using immunofluorescence. We observed that the SLC30A8 protein partly localizes to the plasma membrane (Figure 1A, S1A). The co-localization Pearson's coefficient compared to the SLC1A5 plasma membrane marker is >0.7 for both SLC30A8 constructs (SLC30A8-SH or SH-SLC30A8). We further used HEK293-JI-SLC12A6 (a known plasma membrane transporter) as control and the Pearson's coefficient is comparable (Figure S1B). However, the protein expression level of SLC30A8-SH is as high as SLC12A6 levels, compared with lower expression levels of SH-SLC30A8. These results show that SLC30A8-SH is partially localized at the plasma membrane in HEK293-JI cells.

Given the critical role of SLC30A8 in metabolism in pancreatic cells and the role of genetic variants in diabetes, we reasoned that HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH cell lines could be used to develop a specific assay for SLC30A8. To that end, we generated additional SLC30A8 mutant cell lines to use as a transport-dead control (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{D110N, D224N}) or that overexpress the two most frequent SLC30A8 mutations in patients with diabetes (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325Q} and HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325W}). We characterize the expression and subcellular

localization of these mutants (Fig. 1A). All mutants are localized partly on the plasma membrane (Pearson's coefficient >0.5). However, while SLC30A8^{D110N, D224N} displays the same expression levels and localization as SLC30A8-SH, both diabetic variants display a significantly lower co-localization with the SLC1A5 marker at the plasma membrane.

Furthermore, the overall expression of the diabetes variants is lower compared to SLC30A8-SH and the transport-dead mutant (Fig. 1B).

3.2. Determination of transport activity of SLC30A8 using imaging-based approaches

To examine the involvement of SLC30A8 in the transport of Zinc, the recombinant HEK293JI-SLC30A8-SH cell line was incubated with FluoZin-3 indicator, a Zinc selective green-fluorescent indicator, which can be used to detect the accumulation of zinc in cytoplasm by means of fluorescence microscopy. After loading the cells with FluoZin-3 indicator, we stimulated them with a Zinc Chloride dose response. The HEK293JI-SLC30A8-SH cell line was processed and analyzed in parallel to the transport-dead double mutant (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{D110N, D224N}) or HEK293-JI-SLC12A6-SH (a known plasma membrane unrelated transporter) and HEK293-JI-WT cell lines. Images of the cell lines reveal an increase of cytoplasmic FluoZin-3 fluorescence specific for HEK293JI-SLC30A8-SH (Fig. 2).

3.3. Assessment of diabetes SLC30A8 variants

Mutations of the SLC30A8 gene result in impaired pancreatic beta cell function leading to defects in insulin secretion that confer susceptibility to diabetes mellitus. As described previously, additional SLC30A8 mutant cell lines have been generated specifically. The two most frequent SLC30A8 mutations in patients with diabetes (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325Q} and HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325W}) have been analyzed related to the zinc uptake using imaging-based approach. Staining for FluoZin-3 and following imaging analysis reveals an increase in cytoplasmic zinc in dose dependent manner, expressed as a percentage of Zinc positive cells, specific for HEK293JI-SLC30A8-SH induced cells versus the transport-dead double mutant HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{D110N, D224N} (Fig. 3). Interestingly, the diabetes mutants (HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325Q} and HEK293-JI-SLC30A8-SH^{R325W}) exhibit higher Zinc accumulation compared to the HEK293JI-SLC30A8-SH.

4. Discussion

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder affecting millions of people worldwide and creates considerable economic burden in most countries. The transporter SLC30A8 has a key role in zinc¹² homeostasis inside human pancreatic beta cells [17,18,21,44]. However, the specific role of SLC30A8 in diabetes is still controversial, since several works show opposite effects of genetic variants associated with a lower or higher T2DM risk [9,16,45–49].

Furthermore, there are multiple unsolved gaps associated with SLC30A8 function in humans [36], given that most studies so far employed rodent models or protein homologues [27,50–57]. It was recently proposed that signaling and regulation of zinc by SLC30A8 may differ in humans compared to rodents, highlighting the importance of using human models to study the function of this target [58,59]. Hence, there is a need to generate improved study models to gain more precise insights into the function of SLC30A8 and to develop novel clinical approaches. Recently, the 3D structure of the human SLC30A8 was solved [19] and, together with new functional assays using human models, they could represent key resources for diabetes drug development targeting SLC30A8.

In this study, we generated a human cell model overexpressing the human SLC30A8 isoform. We detected that upon induction of the protein overexpression with doxycycline, SLC30A8 partially localizes to the

Fig. 1. Characterization of cell lines overexpressing SLC30A8 and SLC30A8 mutants. A) Confocal microscopy images of HEK293 Jump-in TREx cells over-expressing SLC30A8 wild type (WT), SLC30A8 transport mutant (D110N, D224N) and SLC30A8 variants involved in diabetes (R325W and R325Q) fused to a TwinStrep-HA (SH) tag at the C terminus. Cells were treated with doxycycline for the duration of the experiment. Anti-SLC1A5 antibody was used to stain the plasma membrane. Scale bar: 20 μ m. B) Quantification of the co-localization signal (Pearson's coefficient) between SLC1A5 and over-expressed tagged proteins indicated. Data shown for fifteen fields from two different wells. Statistical significance was calculated using Dunnett's test and was corrected for multiple testing with the Benjamini-Hochberg correction. *** $P \leq 0.001$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, * $P \leq 0.05$, n.s., not significant.

plasma membrane. This allowed us to investigate an imaging approach based on a Zinc fluorescent dye to follow zinc flux across the plasma membrane, thus developing a novel functional cell-based assay for human SLC30A8. Unlike other plate reader-based assays that measure the signal produced by a cell population, the microscopy allows to measure signal coming from each single cell increasing the sensitivity of the readout (detection of a specific signal reducing unspecific background). Therefore, live cell imaging provides a powerful approach applied for the SLC30A8 functional characterization.

However, we had to overcome several challenges while developing this assay. First, SLC30A8 is naturally located in the membrane of intracellular vesicles in human pancreatic β -cells and other cells models [17,18,21,44,60]. Consequently, these cell models are not suitable for high-throughput SLC30A8 functional assay development, since it is very challenging to characterize a target in internal membranes using existing approaches, especially in primary cell lines. Future studies would also be needed to address how to transfer the results for our assays to the other cellular models of diabetes or pancreatic beta cells. Furthermore, potential SLC30A8 modulators found using our assay, would need to be further validated in the proper disease models.

To develop our assay, we exploited that SLC30A8 is partially localized on the plasma membrane in our cell model. However, the exact

mechanism of this localization remains unclear. On one hand, we speculate that this could be a cause of the overexpression of SLC30A8 in our immortalized cell line, since the large amount of an expressed protein could drive it to localize on plasma membrane. On the other hand, we observed a higher protein abundance on the plasma membrane in the SLC30A8 tagged at the C-terminus with the SH tag. It has been reported that the C terminal region of SLC308A plays a fundamental role in the SLC30A8 function [9,22,61]. Alternatively, it could also be a combined effect from both the fusion tag at the C terminus of SLC30A8 and the recombinant protein overexpression, given that we also observed a small amount of SLC30A8 on the plasma membrane when tagging SLC30A8 at the N-terminus (Figure S1). In any case, additional efforts would be necessary to explore the exact mechanism of this phenomenon.

We also observed that induction of SLC30A8 overexpression with a high dose of doxycycline seemed to produce a deleterious effect for the cells. Therefore, it was crucial to keep transgene expression low during cell line generation and maintenance. By taking advantage of the T-REX tetracycline-inducible gene expression system, we were able to induce SLC30A8 expression only shortly before functional analysis. In addition, the cytotoxicity induced by zinc influx in the cytoplasm consequent to SLC30A8 activation makes a real time detection system the 'conditio sine qua non' for the SLC30A8 functional assay development, otherwise

Fig. 2. Characterization of SLC30A8 transporter activity with FluoZin-3 dye. A) Representative images of HEK293 Jump-in TREx cells over-expressing SLC30A8-SH, SLC30A8-SH^{D110N D224N}, SLC12A6-SH and HEK293 Jump-in TREx *wild type* (WT), in presence (Ind) or absence (Unind) of doxycycline (Dox). B) Fitting curves representing the percentage of Zinc positive cells upon ZnCl₂ dose-response stimulation. HEK Jump-in TREx over-expressing the SLCs constructs were induced with Dox or uninduced as negative control. C) Histogram representing the percentage of Zinc positive cells at 5 mM concentration of ZnCl₂ in HEK 293 Jump-in TREx cells expressing the SLCs constructs and WT cell line upon induction with Dox. Statistical significance was calculated using the Anova test. **** $P \leq 0.0001$, *** $P \leq 0.001$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, * $P \leq 0.05$. The error bars represent the standard deviation (SD) of four technical replicates ($n = 4$).

the accumulation of zinc in the cytoplasm would cause cell death. To further increase the throughput of the assay, a time course of Zinc influx could be studied to determine the optimal timepoint to process cells before cytotoxicity effects become apparent.

Another issue we encountered is represented by the ubiquitous endogenous expression of different Zinc transporters (belonging both to SLC30 and SLC39 families) in HEK293 JI (data publicly available at <https://re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene>). This makes SLC30A8 characterization in a recombinant expression system (live cells) very critical, since similar endogenous unspecific transporters interfere and overlap in the detection of specific SLC30A8-overexpressed functionality [52,59, 60].

In summary, this study demonstrates the potential of a fluorescent Zinc dye-based transport assay using live cell imaging approach to

characterize a Zinc transporter such as SLC30A8. Our novel assay can be further explored and optimized, paving the way for future small molecule medium-throughput screening. Furthermore, several variants affecting the protein function or involved in diabetes mellitus could be studied using this novel assay. Hence, this work represents an alternative to conventional uptake assays and a useful tool for the drug discovery on SLC30A8.

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Fig. 3. Characterization of diabetes associated SLC30A8 variants in Zinc transport activity. A) Representative images of HEK293 Jump-in TReX cells over-expressing SLC30A8-SH, SLC30A8-SH^{D110N D224N}, SLC30A8-SH^{R325W}, SLC30A8-SH^{R325Q} and HEK293 Jump-in TReX wild type (WT), induced with Dox. B) Fitting curves representing the percentage of Zinc positive cells upon ZnCl₂ dose-response stimulation. HEK Jump-in TReX over-expressing the SLCs constructs were induced with Dox. C) Histogram representing the percentage of Zinc positive cells at 5 mM concentration of ZnCl₂. HEK 293 Jump-in TReX expressing the SLCs constructs upon induction with Dox. Statistical significance was calculated using the Anova test. **** $P \leq 0.0001$, *** $P \leq 0.001$, ** $P \leq 0.01$, * $P \leq 0.05$. The error bars represent the standard deviation (SD) of four technical replicates ($n = 4$).

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lucia Azzollini: Writing – original draft, Project administration. **Dolores Del Prete:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Gernot Wolf:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christoph Klimek:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mattia Saggiaro:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Fernanda Ricci:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Eirini Christodoulaki:** Methodology, Investigation. **Tabea Wiedmer:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Alvaro Ingles-Prieto:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Giulio Superti-Furga:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Lia Scarabottolo:** Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.slasd.2024.100166.

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